

**A STUDY OF BRAND IDENTITY & BRAND POSITIONING AS A PART OF
BRAND MANAGEMENT FOR BUILDING BRANDS CONCERNING
ENGINEERING SMES. AN EMPIRICAL STUDY FOCUSING ON SMES FROM
PUNE (MAHARASHTRA, INDIA)**

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Abstract

The role of Brand Management, when it comes to SMEs, is significantly underutilized and ignored. Based on various research findings, SMEs are not following the scientific process of Brand Positioning, Brand Promotion, and Brand Management compared to big corporate brands.

Studying the effects of brand identity and brand positioning as a part of the overall process of Brand Management on the brand development process employed by SMEs is one of the study's main objectives. The second purpose is to comprehend how much the overall brand identity and positioning influence enhancing or growing the brand value in the targeted markets. Other goals include researching the crucial and significant facets of brand positioning that set certain companies apart from rivals and presenting Engineering SMEs with a conceptual process model of brand management.

Various statistical techniques are used for data analysis and interpretation. The Hypothesis is tested using Regression analysis, Factor analysis, and ANOVA. The study also presents the reliability and validity of the relation between identified variables and brand building. For this study, out of the proposed four variables in the Brand Management Process Model, the first variable, 'Brand Identity & Brand Positioning,' is used to test its effect on the brand-building process.

With the lack of awareness and knowledge about progressive brand management methods, Engineering SMEs tend to follow a few initiatives related to brand building based on superficial thinking and a lack of a long-term brand-building strategy. The factor analysis sufficiently proves that SMEs do not give the necessary weightage to defining the factors like Brand Promise, Brand Values, Brand Positioning, or Internal Branding. This research paper also proposes the Brand Management Process Model, the research platform with the projected benefits for Engineering SMEs.

Keywords: Brand Management, Brand Identity, Brand Positioning, Engineering SMEs, Brand Value.

1. Introduction

In today's ever-increasing competitive markets, particularly with the internet revolution and e-commerce mode of trading, brand perception plays a significant role in selecting a preferred brand while making a purchase decision by the consumer.

A brand is the face of the business and its offered products or services. Brand identity is the visual component of a brand representing the core idea, the theme of the services/products it means. Brand perception refers to the customer's opinion of the Brand. It summarizes how customers feel about the Brand, including every direct or indirect experience they have with it. Brand perception is built over time and managed by the brand Management process. Brand management is creating, managing, and improving a brand. Brand management has become one of the most critical aspects of business strategy. It is a specific area of marketing that uses special techniques to increase the perceived value of a brand. Branding and brand-based differentiation are powerful means for creating and sustaining a competitive advantage. Brand awareness, as one of the fundamental dimensions of brand equity, is often considered to be a prerequisite for consumers' buying decisions.

Now, let's see how Brand Identity and Brand Positioning contribute toward forming a unique brand perception and complement the brand-building process.

The brand identity represents its core theme through elements like logo style, colour palette, font, mascot, packaging, tagline, business card, letterhead, slogans, etc. All the aspects should seamlessly fit into the overall theme of the identity. Brands are incomplete and inconsistent if these elements aren't clearly defined or coordinated. Brand elements together develop the proper recognition for the Brand. All these elements act as referral points or reminders sub-contentiously for the customers to recognize the Brand. The Brand should have its values. Brand values determine the Brand's overall identity, message, and personality. These brand principles guide story, actions, behaviours, and decision-making processes. A brand is considered valuable if it's;

- Highly recognizable (people know who they are)
- Positively perceived (people have a good view of them)
- Popular (people buy and use the products or services)
- Have a loyal following (customers are ambassadors of the Brand)

Brand positioning helps create a unique brand perception in the mind of customers. Based on its competitive landscape in the focused markets, the Brand has to communicate its unique offering to set the Brand apart from its competition.

According to the 2018 State of Branding Report, "89 per cent of brand marketers concerned about creating engaging brand experiences and 77 per cent of B2B marketing leaders convinced that branding is critical to growth", clearly highlighting the importance of Brand Positioning. In addition to the critical element of customer recognition, brand positioning is essential for businesses in four ways:

- Market differentiation
- Easy purchase decisions
- Value confirmation

- Magnified messaging

The brand promotion strategy must include a brand promise. It enhances the appeal and relatability of the organization by expanding upon the positioning statement of the business. Brand storytelling is the art of connecting with customers through a narrative that expresses values and what the Brand represents. Marketing communication and promotion collaterals like corporate profiles, product literature, and online presence through websites, social media, emailers, advertisements, etc., also play an essential role in building the desired brand image in customers' minds.

Internal Branding & Employee Perception are other aspects companies tend to ignore, mainly engineering SMEs. Internal branding empowers staff members to represent a complete understanding of brand identity, brand values, brand positioning, product or services offering, customer profiles, etc. Internal branding enables them to act as brand ambassadors who contribute towards establishing desired brand positioning and spreading the right brand image in the market. An internal branding strategy offers employees a reason to support the Brand and make it more vibrant. Using internal brand-building methods effectively is critical for optimizing brand presence.

Engineering SMEs (Small to Medium Enterprises) are the backbone for the existing and future high-growth businesses, with both domestic and foreign companies investing in the 'Make in India' initiative and making a significant impact in the area of indigenization. Made in India with zero defects and zero effects is an important opportunity. The engineering cluster is expected to provide a business ecosystem that enables and continuously supports SMEs in the manufacturing sector that is geared to deliver the right product, the right quality, the right solution, and exemplary service at a competitive price both in domestic and international markets. Engineering SMEs in Pune are engaged in the manufacturing of auto components, locomotives, Agro-based products, machine tools, measuring systems, electronic consumer durables, pharmaceuticals, chemicals, and IT software, among others. Around 61% of the private limited companies belong to the turnover range of 10 - 100 mn. In the last few years, proprietary firms showed the highest revenue growth of 37%, followed by private limited companies (33%).

2. Literature Review

Branding allows consumers to recognize a product quickly and collectively they are aware of or one they like. It acts as a reminder enabling consumers to access relevant information from memory. Branding and brand-based differentiation are powerful means for creating and sustaining a competitive advantage(Chovanová, Korshunov, & Babčanová, 2015). Research advocates that firms should apply strategies based on sensorial aspects in brand communication and promotion. Sensory marketing allows the company, through means such as sensors, sensations, and sensory expressions, to differentiate the brand positioning in the target audience's mind as an image of the multi-sensory brand-experience theme. It offers opportunities for managers to identify emotional/psychological linkages in differentiating, distinguishing, and positioning a brand as an image(Hultén, 2011). Brand equity, value, and quality do not affect brand satisfaction but affect trust. Brand satisfaction involves only

affective commitment, and trust affects commitment and continuance commitment. (Erciş, Ünal, Candan, & Yıldırım, 2012). Brand managers should recognize the role of multi-cultural context in establishing the consumer's perception of commercial brands and develop a well-defined brand personality that conveys the beliefs and values of respective cultures (Anees Ahmad, 2014).

Four variables dominate the use of branding applications in SMEs; characteristics of the SME, the role of customer importance, the role of management and staff, and brand equity. SMEs have a strong desire to use their branding as a tool to develop their businesses. Still, SMEs' primary reasons that restrict their branding budgets are lack of funding, lack of available time or knowledge, lack of experience, and lack of required priority (Horan, O'Dwyer, & Tiernan, 2011). In the SME Structure, the founders' values and beliefs set the tone for the core competencies to be developed and transmitted through brand identity (Spence & Hamzaoui Essoussi, 2010). SMEs can build a brand with smaller resources by being innovative, using affordable communication, and focusing branding efforts on the right segments. The Brand adds value and differentiation from competitors. Branding is an active and continuous process fed by innovations and product differentiation (Franc Vidic, 2013).

Table 1: Review of Literature on the Significant Role of Brand Identity & Positioning in Building Brands of Engineering SMEs

Sr. No.	Focus	Author and Reference
1	In today's digital world, customers are the driving force. The brands offer maximum satisfaction and lower pricing and ensure the rewarding experience will survive. The average Brand without an identity will no longer have any standing in the market.	(Kapferer, 2008)
2	The marketing and branding of SMEs differ from the marketing of large companies. Branding does exist among SMEs at a fundamental level, which is more related to product branding; it requires a lot of strategic planning. Also, it is essential to build brand value in the customers' minds.	(Ahonen, 2008)
3	From a holistic perspective, successful brand management in SMEs consists of five analytical categories that allow an integrated approach, i.e., Brand conception, Brand organization, Brand strategies, Brand building, Brand evaluation, and improvement. The four combined brand-building efforts (Brand identities, Integrated marketing communications, Marketing programs, and Secondary associations) influence SMEs' performance the most.	(Odoom, 2016)

4	Companies must be proactive in building strong brand identity by integrating branding, reputation building, and relevant and appropriate organizational identity as a part of their progression. Also, organizations must express and embed their brand value propositions within their identity and marketing communication while dealing with customers.	(Abimbola et al., 2007)
5	The predefined core values are the guiding principles for aligning resources and tasks to make crucial decisions related to brand enhancement. Value-driven brand management enhances brand trust.	(Eggers et al., 2013)
6	Brand loyalty is achieved through a strong brand positioning around values like 'unique, credible, sustainable,' etc.	(Dr.Babaraju. K.Bhatt,2014)
7	Online Brand Activations are more cost-effective than offline activations, and it is easy to trace the participants of the activations and measure the outcome through campaign analytics.	(Gunawardane & K, 2020)
8	Brand managers are no more looking at brands simply as a selling tool for their products or services; instead, they are looking at the level of Brand engagement with customers.	(Veloutsou & Guzman, 2017)

2.1 Research Gap

Although many research studies are available on Brand Building and Branding relations with marketing initiatives, very few studies talk about Brand identity and Brand positioning as a part of a complete Brand management process model for engineering SMEs. Referring to the literature review and empirical findings does not represent a comprehensive and interpretive solution for Brand Management for SMEs. It raises the need for more data and contributions to describe what happens related to Brand identity and positioning in the SME context. There is a requirement for in-depth research to propose a definite road map for the brand management process keeping the Engineering SMEs focused on building their brands along with achieving & sustaining their brand value in today's competitive environment.

3. Research Problem and Need of the Research

The role of Brand identity and Brand Positioning, when it comes to SMEs, is significantly underutilized and ignored. Based on various research findings, SMEs are not following the scientific process of Brand identity and Brand Positioning as a part of the overall process of Brand Management compared to big corporate brands. Importance is given to setting up manufacturing infrastructure, distribution, required investments, quality control, etc. Brand Identity and Brand Positioning Processes are ignored or addressed with a narrow and superficial vision. In reality, the role of Brand Identity and Brand Positioning is dynamic in creating the desired brand image and sustaining the brand preference in customers' minds.

Thus, the research findings will help establish the importance of the role of Brand Management for SMEs in the Engineering Sector.

4. Objectives

- To study the impact of Brand identity and Brand Positioning on Brand Building Processes used by SMEs
- To study the critical and influential aspects of Brand Identity and Brand Positioning that differentiate the brands from their competition.
- To propose a conceptual process model of brand management to Engineering SMEs.

5. Research Methodology

Considering the nature of the research, which revolves around subjectivity and perception-based decision-making processes, the Quantitative research methodology is adopted. Through convenience sampling, 83 SME respondents (sample size) primary data is gathered. Data from both primary and secondary sources are used in this study. A structured Questionnaire based on the Likert Scale is used to acquire the preliminary data. Secondary data is obtained from various books, articles, journals, and websites. An exploratory approach for secondary data and an empirical approach for the primary data are used to organize and analyze the acquired data for the investigation.

5.1 Proposed Brand Management Process Model for Research

As the brand management process is ongoing, the objectives need to be revisited from time to time, re-engineer the brand communication to align with the marketing insights, and continuously improved to achieve the desired brand image for sustainable growth. In this context, a conceptual Brand Management Process Model, BMPM, has been suggested, shown in Fig. 1, as a part of the research framework. This BMPM comprises four stages. Each stage emphasizes certain areas to build the necessary understanding of Brand identity, Brand communication, and Brand building. This conceptual framework is built according to a holistic perspective of BM. It allows the identification of process flow and makes the empirical data to analyze the gaps in current practices followed by SMEs.

Fig.1: Brand Management Process Model

Fig.2: Brand Management Process Model – Research Stages

5.3 Research Instrument

The sample research study is conducted to test the reliability and validity of the relation between identified variables and Brand building. For this sample study, out of the proposed four variables, the first variable, 'Brand Identity & Brand Positioning,' was used to test its effect on the Brand building process. The research questionnaire was developed based on 7-point Likert Scale along with ten different factors related to Brand Identity & Brand Positioning.

5.4 Hypotheses

The following Hypothesis is developed for the current investigation:

H0 – *"Brand Identity and Brand Positioning does not significantly impact building the Brand of Engineering SMEs of Pune."*

H1 – *"Brand Identity and Brand Positioning do have a significant impact on building the Brands of Engineering SMEs of Pune."*

5.5 Statistical Techniques

The data is analyzed using statistical techniques like percentages, tabular, and graphical methods. To examine the study data and test the Hypothesis, statistical techniques like Regression analysis, Factor analysis, ANOVA, and SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) are used.

6. Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1

1 - Does your Brand Identity (Brand Logo) represent any meaning, definition, or personality of your business idea?					
		Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	1	5.6	5.6	5.6
	2	1	5.6	5.6	11.1
	5	4	22.2	22.2	33.3
	6	5	27.8	27.8	61.1
	7	7	38.9	38.9	100.0
	Total	18	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: Most respondents think that brand identity represents the definition or personality of their business idea. 27.8% and 22.2% give ratings of 6 and 5, respectively, that they think brand identity represents a definition of their business idea. Only 5.6% of respondents gave ratings 1 and 2.

Table 2

2 - Does your Brand Logo have a tagline summarising the core benefit to the customer?					
		Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	4	22.2	22.2	22.2
	2	1	5.6	5.6	27.8
	3	1	5.6	5.6	33.3
	5	4	22.2	22.2	55.6
	6	1	5.6	5.6	61.1
	7	7	38.9	38.9	100.0
	Total	18	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: Most respondents think their Brand Logo carries a tagline summarising the core benefit to the customer. 5.6% of respondents gave a rating of 6. Only four respondents believe that the brand tagline does not benefit the customers.

Table 3

3 - Does your Brand reciprocate a particular set of values? Does your customer community identify your Brand against a few values like Trust, Quality, Reliability, Fare, Professional, Cost-Effectiveness, etc.?					
		Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	4	1	5.6	5.6	5.6
	5	7	38.9	38.9	44.4
	6	6	33.3	33.3	77.8
	7	4	22.2	22.2	100.0
	Total	18	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: Most of the respondents gave a rating of 5, and 33.3% of respondents gave a rating of 6 to this question as they think their Brand reciprocates a set of values. And only 5.6% of respondents feel their Brand does not return any value.

Table 4

4 - Does your Brand have a particular contract in its delivery of values, and how much does this promise gets fulfilled?					
		Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	1	5.6	5.6	5.6
	4	1	5.6	5.6	11.1
	5	1	5.6	5.6	16.7
	6	11	61.1	61.1	77.8
	7	4	22.2	22.2	100.0
	Total	18	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: More than 60% of respondents rated 6 to this question as they think their Brand has a specific promise in terms of its delivery values. Only 5.6% of respondents rated one as they believe there is no need for a particular promise for their Brand.

Table 5

5 - Do you have your Brand Positioning Statement defined, and accordingly, is the Brand positioned in the market within the competitor landscape?					
		Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	3	16.7	16.7	16.7
	2	5	27.8	27.8	44.4

	5	7	38.9	38.9	83.3
	6	1	5.6	5.6	88.9
	7	2	11.1	11.1	100.0
	Total	18	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: Only two respondents gave a rating of 7 to this question. More than 35% of respondents rated five as they think brand positioning is essential in the market within the competitor landscape. Only 16.7% of respondents rated one as they do not believe brand positioning is vital in the market.

Table 6

6 - Is your website updated and covers all the information related to your brand offerings? Is it professionally done and carries a very high and lasting impact?					
		Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	5	27.8	27.8	27.8
	5	1	5.6	5.6	33.3
	6	6	33.3	33.3	66.7
	7	6	33.3	33.3	100.0
	Total	18	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: More than 30% of respondents gave ratings 6 and 7 to this question as they think updating the website is necessary and covers all the information related to their brand offerings. And only five respondents gave a rating of 1 to this question, as they think there is no need to update the website.

Table 7

7 - Do you have your company's social media pages, and is it updated regularly and professionally? Is your social media follower's community representing the target audience of your brand communication?					
		Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	2	11.1	11.1	11.1
	3	4	22.2	22.2	33.3
	5	2	11.1	11.1	44.4
	6	7	38.9	38.9	83.3
	7	3	16.7	16.7	100.0
	Total	18	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: Most respondents think that the social media followers' community represents the target audience of their brand communication. 16.7% of respondents gave a rating of 7 to this question. Only 11.1% and 22.2% of respondents gave ratings 1 and 3, respectively, as they don't have a company social media page or don't think social media can represent the target audience of their brand communication.

Table 8

8 - How much awareness do your employees have about your Brand Identity, Brand Promise, Brand Positioning, etc.?					
		Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	1	5.6	5.6	5.6
	2	1	5.6	5.6	11.1
	4	2	11.1	11.1	22.2
	5	9	50.0	50.0	72.2
	6	4	22.2	22.2	94.4
	7	1	5.6	5.6	100.0
	Total	18	100.0	100.0	100.0

Interpretation: Almost 50% of respondents rated 5 to this question as they think their employees have awareness about their Brand Identity, Brand Promise, Brand Positioning, etc. 5.6% of respondents believe that there is no need for brand awareness for their employees about their brand identity, brand promise, brand positioning, etc.

Table 9: Factor Analysis

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings	
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance
1	3.826	42.517	42.517	3.826	42.517
2	1.778	19.756	62.273	1.778	19.756
3	.991	11.008	73.281		
4	.819	9.105	82.386		
5	.617	6.850	89.236		
6	.419	4.659	93.895		
7	.265	2.945	96.840		
8	.181	2.007	98.848		
9	.104	1.152	100.000		

Interpretation: From the above factor table, we can see that two values have more than one Eigenvalue. So, we can consider those factors to be computed from the factor analysis.

Table 10: Communalities

Communalities		
	Initial	Extraction
Question 1 - Brand Identity Expression	1.000	.528
Question 2 - Brand Tag Line expressing the core benefit	1.000	.573

Question 3 - Brand values	1.000	.204
Question 4 - Brand Promise	1.000	.641
Question 5 - Brand Positioning Statement	1.000	.802
Question 6 - Website updates & their lasting impact?	1.000	.838
Question 8 – Internal Brand Awareness	1.000	.481

Interpretation: Communalities show the degree of variation in each variable that is accounted for. Here, Principal Component Analysis is used as the Extraction Method. Initial communalities are estimates of the variation in each variable that all components or factors can explain. For correlation studies, this is always equal to 1.0 for principal component extraction. The communalities in the above table are all high, indicating that the extracted components accurately reflect the variables.

Table 11

Rotated Component Matrix		
	Component	
Question 6 - Website updates & their lasting impact	.915	
Question 2 - Brand Tag Line expressing the core benefit	.716	
Question 8- Internal Brand Awareness	.692	
Question 5 - Brand Positioning Statement	.663	.602
Question 4 - Brand Promise		.756
Question 1 - Brand Identity Expression		-.726
Question 3 - Brand Values		.448

Interpretation: Highest value is for component website updates & their lasting impact, which is .915, and the lowest is -0.756 for Brand Promise shows the effects of variables.

Table 12

Regression Model Summary				
Model (Variable)	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. error of the Estimate
Brand Identity & Brand Positioning	.354^a	.125	.070	1.67925

Interpretation: R denotes the association between directed and independent variables. The meaning, in this case, is .354, indicating a 35.4% favourable association between independent and dependent variables. R-Squared shows the total variation for a dependent variable that an

independent variable can explain. In this case, the value is .125, which is good. In this case, the value of Adjusted R Square is .070, which is not far from .426, so this is also satisfactory.

Table 13

ANOVA						
Model (Variable)		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Brand Identity & Brand Positioning	Regression	6.445	1	6.445	2.286	.040 ^b
	Residual	45.118	16	2.820		
	Total	51.563	17			

Interpretation: P-value/Sig value: For the significance level analysis, 95 per cent confidence intervals or 5 per cent are chosen. As a consequence, the p-value must be smaller than 0.05. It is 0.040 in the table above. As a consequence, the outcome is critical.

F-ratio: This suggests an increase in the calculation of the variables by setting the formula by accounting for the model's inaccuracy. For the efficient model, the F-ratio yield is more significant. The meaning in the table above is 2.286, which is satisfactory.

In the context of this study, P-value (sig. value) is 0.04, which is <0.05, which means that our alternate Hypothesis is Accepted. Brand Identity and Brand Positioning significantly impact the building of the brands of Engineering SMEs of Pune.

Table 14

Coefficients					
Model (Variable)	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Brand Identity & Brand Positioning	.163	2.853		.057	.955
	.816	.540	.354	1.512	.150

Interpretation: It is interpreted from the above table that Brand Identity and Brand Positioning do have a significant impact on building the Brand of Engineering SMEs of Pune.

T (17) = 1.515, p < .05.

7. Discussions and Results

Most respondents believe that brand identity embodies the definition or personality of their business concept. Most respondents believe that their Brand's logo includes a tagline that summarises the core brand value to the client. A set of values are reciprocated by their Brand, according to 33.3% of respondents. More than 60% of respondents believe that their Brand makes a specific promise about the core brand value and its delivery. More than 35% of respondents believe that brand positioning is crucial in the market, given the competitors' landscape. More than 30% of respondents believe upgrading the website to provide all the information about their brand offerings is vital. Most respondents believe that the community of social media users represents the intended audience for their Brand's communications. Nearly 50% of respondents think their staff members know their Brand's identity, promise, positioning, etc.

Since all the commonalities are high, the extracted components must precisely reflect the variables. There are multiple Eigenvalues for two values. Therefore, we can consider those when computing the factors for our factor analysis. The correlation coefficient between the independent and dependent variables is 35.4%, or .354. R-Squared (.125) demonstrates the total amount of variation for a dependent variable that an independent variable can account for is favourable. The F-ratio yield for the efficient model is more substantial, coming in at 2.286, which is good. P-value (sig. value) in this investigation is 0.04, which is less than 0.05, and $t(17) = 1.515$ ($p < .05$), indicating that our alternative Hypothesis is accepted. The development of the Brand of Pune-based engineering SMEs is thus significantly impacted by brand identity and positioning. In our investigation, the distribution's spread is regulated by the standard deviation of 0.970. We got the evaluation point (z) and two distributions (f and g). The conceptual framework of the brand management process enables process flow identification and makes it possible to analyze empirical data to identify gaps in the practices being used by SMEs.

8. Conclusion and Suggestions

With the lack of awareness and knowledge about progressive methods of Brand Management Engineering, SMEs tend to follow a few initiatives related to Brand building based on superficial thinking and lack to build a long-term brand-building strategy. The factor analysis sufficiently proves that SMEs do not give the necessary weightage to defining the factors like Brand Promise, Brand Values, Brand Positioning, or Internal Branding. In this paper, the empirical study is based on Brand Identity & Brand Positioning as one variable presented in the proposed Brand Management Process Model affecting brand building. It represents the positive results and supports the alternate Hypothesis. The proposed Brand Management Process Model will act as a research platform to implement an in-depth study for various aspects related to Brand Identity & Brand Positioning, Market Insights & Brand Building Strategy, Sales Promotion, and Interpreting Brand Performance.

Based on the study, we have some recommendations. The activities that SMEs carry out to develop their brands should increase. Most SMEs are owner-operated, driven by the owner's passion, personality, and principles. Brand management must personify to prevent a disconnect between the brand promise and the customer experience. The Brand management goals need to be set based on the individuals selected to lead the branding function, their familiarity and their knowledge of brand management. Similar to how they manage their balance sheets, SMEs

must develop and maintain their brand brand-building initiatives. As products are produced on assembly lines, the brand promise or brand positioning serves as the key differentiator in the competitive landscape.

9. Limitations

The following are some of the study's limitations:

1. The researcher had limited access to several organizations and their internal documents.
2. The research had to be restricted to limited SMEs in Pune due to budget constraints, time frames, and other resources.
3. The case study approach and semi-structured interviews' characteristically small sample sizes are other significant research drawback. This impacts the result's generalizability.
4. Using more than one observer to gather data will boost the study's dependability regarding the data obtained through observation.

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